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Agricultural Diversification at the Margin. Strategies and Determinants in Italian Mountain and Remote Areas

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the convergence in on-farm diversification strategies of agricultural holdings, between remote areas and more central ones. Using Italian farm-level data, we explore the determinants of diversification strategies across farms. Remoteness is defined using two variables: geographical remoteness (location in mountain areas) and remoteness from the urban poles providing public services (inner areas). Results show that farmers in remote areas are more likely to diversify crop production, but the overall magnitude of this difference is small. With regard to the inseparable non-agricultural secondary activities, the core-periphery differences are significant only in mountain areas. Inseparable non-agricultural secondary activities are uncorrelated to commodity prices and produce larger value-added and should be encouraged across marginal areas.

JEL Classification: L25, O18, Q12

1 | Introduction

While the contribution of agriculture to national GDP is declining in all developed countries, the primary sector is still relevant in many rural and marginal areas. Agriculture does not benefit from agglomeration economies (Krugman 1991) and suffers from increasingly erratic climate conditions, which negatively affects productivity (Auffhammer and Schlenker 2014; Reidsma et al. 2010; EEA 2019; IPCC 2022; Coderoni and Pagliacci 2023). Thus, income stabilization tools are crucial for farm households. One strategy which is available for farmers is agricultural diversification, which helps mitigate income fluctuations by spreading the risk across different crops or activities. In this respect, diversification is a form of insurance towards the risks of monocultures or single-farm business, which is sensitive to price changes or weather conditions. Diversification also represents an example of adaptation strategy to climate change, as weather conditions are increasingly affecting farm income stability (McNamara and Weiss 2005).

In general, diversification is divided into on-farm and off-farm activities (Ullah and Shivakoti 2014). On-farm diversification includes all economic activities that are developed with farm's capital. This includes crop diversification, agritourism, energy production, direct sales, etc. Off-farm diversification occurs when farmers have part-time jobs off the farm, so that their income is no longer entirely dependent on the farm's capital but includes non-agricultural components. Not all definitions agree on the on-farm and off-farm meaning (e.g., Tittonell et al. 2010).

Understanding the level of diversification in marginal and remote areas is relevant. Geographically isolated places lag behind in terms of socioeconomic development and access to public services (Bocco 2016). As the income of remote communities relies on agriculture, diversified and efficient farms are of utmost importance and may, under some specific circumstances, help reduce depopulation processes (Pagliacci and Fasano 2023).

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At the present state of the art, the association between remoteness and diversification is unclear. Remoteness is often studied by proxies, for example, urbanization using indexes. Both Ahearn et al. (2006) and Goodwin and Mishra (2004) found no association between remoteness and diversification in United States agriculture. Khanal and Mishra (2014) found that farms in US metro counties (i.e., counties with higher population density) are less likely to engage in agritourism and more likely to go off-farm as a strategy to reduce income volatility.

In Europe, El Benni and Schmid (2022) found that farms in mountain areas in Switzerland were less likely to diversify than those located in flat plains, while another study found that mountain farms were more likely to search for off-farm income (Mann 2009). In Italy, research conducted by Mazzocchi et al. (2020) used the Van der Ploeg and Roep (2003) model to understand choices of the diversified farms and found that mountain farms were more likely to engage in broadening activities and less likely to undertake deepening or re-grounding. In Germany, Meraner et al. (2018) found a positive association between residence in a remote area and the intensity of diversification. Overall, this brief review of studies indicates that results are mixed.

In addition, the concept of remoteness is evolving as policy-makers have adopted newer definitions based on some socio-demographic indicators and on accessibility (e.g., Copus and Crabtree 1996; Koomen 2011).

This paper aims to contribute to the existing scientific literature on diversification. To do so, this paper undertakes an econometric analysis of farm-level data to explore the determinants of both crop diversification and diversification in Inseparable Nonagricultural Secondary (hereinafter, INAS) activities. It aims to disentangle differences between remote and central areas across Italy. Italy represents an interesting case study, because of its large heterogeneity. In addition to its core-periphery structure, which turns into great income inequality between North and South, between urban and rural areas, and between central and remote areas (Iammarino et al. 2019; Ballatore and Mariani 2019; Gallo and Pagliacci 2020), the country also shows large differences in climatic conditions (Cubasch et al. 1996), in soil and topographical features, as well in structural characteristic of the agricultural sector (Bozzola et al. 2018). Thus, investigating diversification choices of farms across these varied conditions is of great interest.

In this study, remote areas are defined based on two indicators: (1) a purely geographical indicator, that is, location in mountain areas, and (2) location in inner areas, according to the definition provided by Italian National Strategy for Inner Areas (hereinafter, NSIA) (Barca et al. 2014), which classifies Italian municipalities according to their distance from urban poles providing essential services. Proxying remoteness by both a purely geographical dimension (mountain areas) and by a definition also encompassing socioeconomic elements (NSIA classification) is one of the main novelties of this analysis. Although inner areas specifically relate to the Italian case, the implications of this study are more general, due to the fact that lack of public services generally characterizes remote lagging-behind

regions all around Europe (Siuruainen 2019; Hernandez and Dávila 2016). The study strives to understand whether successful diversification patterns may be identified for marginal areas, and provides policy guidance to generate additional income at the local level, and to improve efficiency of the farming system in such areas, as a tool to reduce development gaps.

2 | Methods and Data

2.1 | Theoretical Framework for Agricultural Diversification and Dependent Variables

In a theoretical model for diversification, farm households are profit-maximizers that try to increase income by allocating labor and investments to multiple activities, either on-farm or off-farm (Singh et al. 1986), the latter being sometimes called pluri-activity (Salvioni et al. 2013). The main reasons to undertake diversification are both risk management and increase of the efficiency. Off-farm work occurs when the marginal income of additional on-farm work declined below the farm household's reservation wage. Decisions to diversify on-farm are based on the scale of production (i.e., the extent to which one activity benefits from economy of scale, Huffman 1980) and economies of scope (i.e., joint productions are less costly than separate productions, Featherstone and Moss 1994). On-farm activity diversification—the topic of this study—encompasses both agricultural (crop) diversification and diversification in connected activities. This distinction is taken from Tiftonell et al. (2010), who distinguish between on-farm activities to refer to crop diversification, and nonfarm activities to indicate INAS activities. However, compared to Tiftonell et al. (2010), we employ a different terminology to avoid potential ambiguity caused by the term *nonfarm*, which may be confused with off-farm work.

A major benefit of diversification in agriculture is income stabilization. Compared to other economic sectors, agriculture is subject to multiple risks, including dependence on weather conditions that affect yields and income. Keeping crop and INAS activities separate is advantageous in disengaging two aspects of agricultural risk. In fact, crop diversification reduces risks from weather and commodity prices fluctuations (Kurdyś-Kujawska et al. 2021), while INAS activities help lessen farmers' reliance on agriculture (Grilli et al. 2024; Bartolini et al. 2014).

To account for both these aspects, two dependent variables are used: (1) an index that captures agricultural diversification (i.e., number of different agricultural crops cultivated at agricultural holding level), and (2) a variable that describes diversification in nonagricultural INAS activities.

2.1.1 | Agricultural Diversification Modeling

The creation of the agricultural diversification index follows the approach proposed by McNamara and Weiss (2005), who define three main diversification indices: (1) the entropy index, (2) the

Berry index, and (3) the modified Concentration ratio. This paper is based on the entropy index, which ranges in the $[0, 1]$ interval.¹ Assuming that $s_j = q_j/Q$ is the share of Utilized Agricultural Area (UAA) q utilized for product j on the total UAA Q , the calculation of the entropy index D_E is performed with the following formula:

$$D_E = \sum_{j=1}^J s_j \log(1/s_j) \quad (1)$$

The j products included in the index are available in the census data (i.e., cereals, legumes, potatoes and beetroots, pastures, fodder and plants, industrial crops, permanent crops).² To model the index, McNamara and Weiss (2005) employ a logit model with robust standard errors to address biased standard errors that originate when the dependent variable is a proportion. Papke and Wooldridge (1996) propose a different methodology, which is based on the logit density function but provides unbiased standard errors. The model is called fractional logit model and is useful when the dependent variable is a proportion in the $[0, 1]$ interval (Aitchison 1986). The fractional logit uses the quasi-binomial distribution. The probability that a farm has a diversification degree y_i is a function of a set of covariates X and a vector of coefficients β to be estimated:

$$\ln \ell(\beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n [y_i \ln(g(X_i\beta)) + (1 - y_i) \ln(1 - g(X_i\beta))] \quad (2)$$

Where $g(X_i\beta)$ represents the logit link function:

$$Pr(Y_i) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-X_i\beta}} \quad (3)$$

2.1.2 | Modeling Inseparable Nonagricultural Secondary Activities

INAS activities are recorded in the agricultural census according to the following categories: (1) health, social, and educational services, (2) agritourism, (3) tourism-related activities, (4) handicraft goods, (5) agricultural product processing, (6) renewable energy, (7) wood processing, (8) aquaculture, (9) contracting, (10) silviculture, and (11) other. The agricultural census does not provide any information about the economic importance of each activity, but only reports the working time that employees dedicate to INAS activities globally and dummy variables that capture whether a particular farm undertakes each activity or not.

Working time is often used as a proxy for the effort that farmers dedicate to some specific activity or for off-farm work (Shaw 1992). The time dedicated to connected activities reflects the opportunity cost, income, and importance attached to that activity (Špička and Dereník 2021). The theoretical approach to model working time follows Špička et al. (2019), who review methods to model farm-level data. The time dedicated to connected activities is a proportion of the total working time, thus fractional models described in equation.³

2.2 | Remoteness and the Impact on Agricultural Diversification

Exploring core-periphery differences requires appropriate measures of remoteness. According to Bocco (2016) there are two broad dimensions of remoteness: (1) an absolute measure of remoteness, which is given by physical distance, and (2) a relative measure, that is, the connectivity of one place in relation to others. The absolute dimension of remoteness is the distance as measured in parallels, altitudes, or meridians, thus related to the geography of the place. The second dimension is instead relative, and it is given by the connectivity and accessibility of one place with its neighbors. Both dimensions contribute to the isolation of a population (which often translates into depopulation). While geographical distance is constant, relative distance may be reduced thanks to public infrastructure and improved transport technologies. To capture this twofold dimensions of remoteness, two variables are included in the estimation models: location in mountain areas and location in an inner area, as defined by the Italian legal framework.

Mountains cover about 35% of the European surface (Price 2016). With regard to agricultural and farming systems, mountain area farms are characterized by high cultivation costs and low yields (Bentivoglio et al. 2019). Over decades, limited agricultural productivity in mountain regions has contributed to a decline in farm economic activities, leading to land abandonment, depopulation, and agricultural decline (MacDonald et al. 2000; Tzanopoulos et al. 2011). Due to these reasons, the EU assigned to mountain communities specific support through the Rural Development Policy and, recently, introduced a voluntary quality scheme for mountain products through the EU Regulation 1151/2012 (Pagliacci et al. 2022).

To capture the relative dimension of remoteness, the models include a dummy variable that captures farm location in inner areas, as defined in the NSIA (Barca et al. 2014; Barone et al. 2023). NSIA is a national policy that promotes cohesion and territorial development, reducing urban-rural disparities (Lucatelli 2016; Bertolini and Pagliacci 2017; Colucci 2018; Iammarino et al. 2019; SVIMEZ 2019; ISTAT 2019). NSIA classifies municipalities into inner or central areas based on the availability of the following local services: (1) availability of a hospital with an emergency service, (2) medium-sized train station, and (3) availability of high schools of all kind (see Pagliacci and Fasano (2023) for a description of the indicator and classification of Italian municipalities). Therefore, inner areas suffer from remoteness, because of the lack of essential services at a reasonable distance. At present, inner areas cover 60% of the Italian land, and 52% of the total municipalities, being home for 22% of the population (Romano et al. 2022).

2.3 | Data

This study uses secondary data provided by the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT). ISTAT collects several databases to monitor trends in the Italian geography, demography, and economy, including the primary sector. The final dataset for the analysis is obtained by merging three data sources:

1. The database that classifies Italian municipalities as inner and central areas. Barca et al. (2014) proposed a six-class taxonomy of inner areas based on travel-time distance from the nearest urban center providing essential services. In this study, the classification is coded in a binary variable that uses a travel-time distance of 20 min to an urban center as a threshold to classify an inner (i.e., remote) municipality compared to a non-inner (i.e., central) one.
2. The database of Italian municipalities with geographical location (mountain area, hilly area, coastline), which is used to classify mountain municipalities.
3. The Agricultural Census data by ISTAT, which records farms' activities, characteristics, and farmers' socio-demographic. Data are retrieved from the 2020 census, that is, the most recent release of census data available at the time of conducting the study.

The determinants of diversification are selected according to the main literature. A recent review of diversification studies collected the set of useful determinants to model diversification choices (Grilli et al. 2024). Starting from that work, three group

of variables are included: geographical determinants, farm-level determinants, owner-level determinants. The full set of variables and their description is available in Table 1.

3 | Results

Table 2 reports the econometric models showing the determinants of agricultural diversification and diversification in INAS activities. All models include regional dummies that capture additional regional-based social and economic characteristics in which each farm is located. As a general interpretation rule, positive coefficients indicate that the given covariate shows a positive impact on diversification, whereas negative coefficients are associated with covariates that decrease diversification at the farm level.

3.1 | Agricultural Diversification

With respect to agricultural (or crop) diversification, the dummy variable that captures farm location in one of the Italian

TABLE 1 | Descriptive statistics of the sample.

Variable	Description	Mean	St. Dev
Dependent Variables			
Entropy	Crop diversification Index	0.41	0.20
Time for connected activities	Share of the total time of workers dedicated to INAS activities	0.05	0.14
Remoteness Variables			
Farm in mountain area	Farm is located in a mountain area	0.34	0.50
Farm in Inner area	Farm is located in an inner area	0.56	0.44
Independent Variables			
% rented land	Share to rented land on the total Utilized Agricultural Area	0.29	0.40
Total UAA	Total Utilized Agricultural Area for farming	39.23	99.01
FTE hours	Full-time equivalent working hours of the employees	2.31	85.61
% of female employees	Share of female workers	0.04	0.14
Amount of support payment	Support payments received from the Common Agricultural Policy	26.03	30.37
Innovative farm	Farm has introduced an innovation within the last 5 years	0.67	0.45
Digital farm	Farm has access to internet and computer	0.20	0.42
Female owner	Farm owner is female	0.29	0.46
Age	Age of the farm owner	55.96	15.45
Owners' days spent on farm	Number of days that the owner spend on on-farm activities	168.59	129.66
Italian citizenship	Farm owner has an Italian citizenship	0.97	0.07
European citizenship	Farm owner has a European citizenship	0.01	0.06
Extra EU citizenship	Farm owner has a non-EU citizenship	0.02	0.03
High school	Farm owner has a high school degree	0.08	0.24
Degree in Agric. science	Farm owner has a university degree in agricultural sciences	0.02	0.14
Other degree	Farm owner has a university degree (nonagricultural)	0.07	0.25
Partner/spouse works on farm	The partner of the owner works on the same farm	0.11	0.31
Population Density	Population density of the municipality where the farm is located	198.34	117.99
Regional FE	Dummies for regional fixed effects included in the model	—	—

TABLE 2 | Crop and INAS activities diversification models.

	Crop Diversification Entropy Index	Time Time
Remoteness variables		
Farm in mountain area	0.176*** (12.87)	0.245*** (8.38)
Inner area	0.0707*** (10.32)	0.115*** (6.91)
Inner area x Mountain area	0.282* (29.32)	0.551*** (25.78)
Local Population density	-0.0381*** (-8.11)	-0.011 (-1.10)
Farm characteristics		
% of rented land	0.190*** (25.73)	0.32*** (19.54)
Total UAA	-0.00127*** (-14.64)	0.000782 (0.27)
FTE hours	0.0284*** (7.69)	-0.0088*** (-4.02)
% of female employees	-0.0002 (-0.71)	0.00032 (0.55)
Amount of support payment	-0.499*** (-6.53)	-6.91*** (-24.58)
Innovative farm	-0.275*** (-21.26)	-0.234*** (-14.99)
Digital farm	0.169*** (21.05)	1.494*** (79.05)
Owner's socio- demographics		
Female	-0.127*** (-20.71)	0.202** (13.27)
Age (ref. Level: less than 40)		
Age 40-65	-0.0153 (-0.85)	-0.210*** (-3.86)
Age > 65	0.226*** (4.39)	-3.860*** (-12.49)
Owners' days spent on farm	0.0272*** (18.42)	-0.147*** (47.28)
Owner's citizenship (ref. Level: Italian)		
EU citizenship (non-Italian)	0.408*** (8.69)	0.404*** (4.96)
Extra-EU citizenship	0.139* (-1.91)	-0.148 (-1.36)

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

	Crop Diversification Entropy Index	Time Time
Education (ref. Level: primary)		
High school	0.0441*** (7.81)	-0.324*** (21.56)
University degree in Agricultural science	0.0859*** (6.12)	0.463*** (14.12)
Other University degree	0.0789*** (3.94)	0.577** (27.06)
Partner/spouse works on farm	0.132*** (8.33)	0.163* (2.25)
Regional FE	Yes	Yes
Constant	2.930*** (120.05)	-2.51*** (-46.38)
LL	-233393	-58905
AIC	466865	8535.5
BIC	467309	8903.8
N	652950	652950

Note: t-statistic in brackets. ***, **, and * indicate 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, respectively.

inner municipalities, with farms in non-inner municipalities as reference level, is positive and statistically significant at 1% confidence level. This result is a strong evidence that on-field diversification of farms in inner areas is generally larger than diversification of farms in non-inner areas. The dummy that controls for farms in mountain areas is also positive, although it is nonsignificant. Furthermore, an interaction term between location in inner area and location in mountain area is positive and significant, thus indicating that farms in inner areas in mountainous regions are more likely diversified, all else held equal.

In terms of farm characteristics, the analysis returns a positive impact of the share of rented UAA on crop diversification, which indicates that farmers who rent land may use it for diversification. The relationship between total UAA and diversification is inverse, which means that larger farms are expected to diversify less on their land. With respect to hired labor, expressed in terms of full-time equivalent employees, farms with larger hired labor is more likely to implement agricultural diversification. The diversification is instead not significantly different at increasing shares of female hired labor. The amount of CAP support payment⁴ received by farmers has a significant negative influence on diversification, all else held equal. Regarding farms' technological level, innovative farms (i.e., farms using at least one digital device) are less likely diversified, whereas agricultural diversification increases when farms have access to digital technologies.

With regard to respondents' socio-demographics, female owners are less likely to adopt agricultural diversification than male

owners. Owners' age does not have a sizeable impact on diversification below 65 years of age, while older owners are more likely to implement agricultural diversification. Nationality is also a personal characteristic that influences diversification, with foreign-led farms more likely to diversify on-field. Educational level of the owners that matters the most: in all models, it is significantly associated with larger diversification. If compared with farmers with a primary education, respondents with a high school degree or a nonagricultural university degree are more likely to diversify with a comparable probability. Farmers who attained a university degree in agricultural science are more likely to undertake diversification compared to farmers with primary education or having a high school degree in nonagricultural fields (reference level).

3.2 | Inseparable Nonagricultural Secondary Activities

Column 3 of Table 2 displays the results for the models for INAS activities. Diversification through INAS activities is not statistically different between farms located in inner and in non-inner areas. Similarly, there are no differences between farms in mountain areas and flat plains or hills. The interaction term between the two variables, which captures farms in mountain areas that are also classified as inner areas, returns a positive and highly significant coefficient. This result suggests that farmers in mountainous inner areas allocate more working time on INAS activities compared to other farmers and, on average, adopt a larger number of diversification activities.

In terms of farm characteristics, time dedicated to INAS activities is influenced by rented land and by the total UAA in opposite directions. Rented land positively affects time spent on INAS activities, while total UAA does not so. The amount of CAP support to the farm shows a negative effect: farmers receiving larger CAP payments and subsidies allocate less time to INAS activities. Similarly to the agricultural diversification models, this impact is however small. Farmers that run innovative farms dedicate less time to INAS activities, while farmers with digital technologies spend more time on INAS activities.

With respect to sociodemographic characteristics of the farm owner, the model indicates that female owners spend more time on INAS activities compared to their male counterparts. When looking at the age, working time on INAS activities significantly declines with older owners. In terms of citizenship, farmers from EU are more likely to spend more time on INAS activities compared to both Italians and non-EU citizens. The impact of educational attainment has a significant positive influence on time spent on INAS activities. On the other hand, having the partner working on-farm increases time spent on other activities.

4 | Discussion

Diversification may be a crucial strategy for farmers located in remote areas, representing a way to increase their income, which is generally lower compared to those located in non-inner areas due to lower agricultural productivity (Cesaro and

Marongiu 2017). There are two main alternatives to diversify agricultural business, which are not mutually exclusive but rather complementary: (1) increase diversification in crops, hence the number of produced agricultural commodities, and (2) diversify on-farm with nonagricultural activities. Farmers do not need additional knowledge to enlarge agricultural diversification, hence this solution might be easier. Agricultural diversification reduces commodity price risks but does not cover from other risks that are specific to the agricultural business, including natural hazards, climate and weather risks. On the other hand, INAS activities are more effective to disentangle farmers' income from primary sector, but they require additional skills compared to the main agricultural activity and more investments. Therefore, diversification choices imply trade-offs.

4.1 | Diversification in Remote Areas

Overall, this study shows that farms in inner areas have larger levels of crop diversification, and this level is statistically significant. However, crop diversification gap between inner and non-inner areas is relatively small. In terms of INAS activities, farms in inner areas are not generally more diversified than those in non-inner areas. The only effect of larger diversification is found in mountain areas. These results can be largely explained by the conditions of the local economy and of the agricultural sector in the inner areas. Productions in inner areas are difficult, in fact revenues per hectare are on average lower compared to non-inner areas (Cesaro and Marongiu 2017). The lower productivity may be driven by both low productivity of capital and labor. With respect to labor, the difficulty in doing business is a migration push factor (Corrado and D'Agostino 2018; Vendemmia et al. 2021), thus reducing the quantity and quality of skilled labor in inner areas. The low productivity is also related to capital inputs, that is, mechanization of agriculture, which might be lower in inner areas. Mechanization is scale-sensitive, hence associated with larger monocultural fields rather than fractionated and diversified land (De Roest et al. 2018). The geographical context of inner areas is often rough and sloped, therefore it is less suitable for mechanized farming compared to the land of farms located in non-inner areas (Lucatelli et al. 2013). In addition, many inner areas are located in Southern Italy, which generally lags behind compared to Central and Northern Italy. For this reason, the opportunity cost of crop differentiation might be lower for farms in Southern regions.

Another explanation might be that farmers in inner areas attempt to stabilize income through additional support payments by participating in Agri-Environmental Schemes (AES) more frequently than farmers of non-inner areas. AES often require environmental benefits that may be achieved through diversification. To the best of our knowledge, the scientific literature lacks of contribution that specifically investigate AES in remote areas, therefore this hypothesis cannot be validated by existing studies but might be an avenue of future research.

The benefits of crop diversification (especially when combined with crop rotation) include larger yields, reduced damages of the total yields due to pests and parasites (Finckh et al. 2000),

better soil health (Poulton et al. 2018), and better resilience of the agricultural business in general (Johnston et al. 1995; Beillouin et al. 2021). However, the exclusive use of crop diversification keeps farmers' income attached to the agricultural performance, and does not allow farmers to adequately reduce a wider range of risks, especially the risks connected with natural hazards or extreme weather events, and sharp variation of agricultural commodity prices (Knapp et al. 2021).

To effectively tackle these additional agricultural risks, it is crucial for farmers to undertake activities that are ancillary to the production of agricultural goods. However, in terms of INAS activities, significant differences between inner and non-inner areas are not observed. The only case of larger diversification in INAS activities is found for inner mountain areas. One explanation might be that farmers in mountain areas are more prone to diversify with tourism-related activities, for which mountain areas are typically well suited (Patarchanov 2012). This is in line with some studies that suggest greater engagement in diversification in INAS activities in Italian mountain farms (Mazzocchi et al. 2020) and agritourism in particular (Sharpley and Vass 2006). Actually, agritourism is just the INAS activity that grew the most in the 2010s, between the last two rounds of the Agricultural Censuses. In the mountain, the natural beauty of the landscape is a valuable resource for inner areas (Cesaro and Marongiu 2017). Agriculture in the mountains is difficult but can be easily complemented with tourism and recreation (Maye et al. 2009).

Another feature of mountain areas is forests. Land use has changed considerably in Italian flat plains but mountains are still primarily forested areas. About 95 percent of forests are located in mountain areas in Italy (Pettenella and Secco 2004). Therefore, silviculture is another INAS activities that is presumably undertaken in the mountains. Silviculture is resilient to many weather events, thus uncorrelated with agriculture in hazard and weather risk management. The low profitability of silviculture in Italy, however, is an important limitation (Tarasconi et al. 2010; Accastello et al. 2018).

Apart from mountain areas, the overall indication of the analysis is that inner area farms put less effort on INAS activities than they do for crop diversification. Agriculture is income inelastic, therefore farmers would not increase their agricultural revenues when the general economy grows (Tiffin and Tiffin 1999). For this reason, the prevailing allocation of farm's capital on agricultural good production is inefficient. Increasing revenues is facilitated by allocating capital or personal labor in activities alternative to agriculture, either in INAS activities on-farm or finding a second job off-farm (Salvioni et al. 2020; McNamara and Weiss 2005).

While inner area farmers undertake larger diversification in agricultural crops than farmers in central areas, this is not the case for diversification in INAS activities. Running INAS activities requires additional skills compared to agricultural productions, which many farmers may not possess. As a possible explanation, one could observe that inner area farmers are less educated than farmers in non-inner areas: the share of inner area farmers with a high school diploma in agriculture is lower than farmers in non-inner areas. Similarly, the number of

farmer who attained a university degree, either in agricultural science or other degrees, is lower. This lower education might reflect lower skills in engaging in alternative activities (Petit and Barghouti 1992). For this reason, strengthening advisory services and the Agricultural Knowledge and Information System (AKIS) is crucial to inform inner area farmers about the benefits of diversifying agricultural activities. Future reforms of the CAP should thus pay increasing attention to this topic.

4.2 | Farm's Determinants of Diversification

The paper sheds further light on some other results of interest. In terms of farm characteristics, it was found an inverse association between farm size and crop diversification. Mechanization is scale positive, hence leading to less diversification in larger farms, despite the 2014–2020 CAP greening measure requirements, which explicitly include also agricultural diversification. Overall, results indicate that small farms diversify more, probably as a survival strategy (Khanal and Mishra 2014).

With respect to innovation, the inverse significant relationship with agricultural diversification possibly suggests that innovation is also scale positive. Innovation automatizes many procedures, and this is also reflected in less time dedicated to INAS activities (Mc Fadden and Gorman 2016). Conversely, Digital farms are more likely engaged in diversification. Digital technologies may be used for online sales that reduce distribution costs, which may compensate efficiency losses due to diversification.

4.3 | The Impact of Sociodemographic Characteristics on Diversification

Regarding personal sociodemographic characteristics, the most interesting findings relate to education. The analysis shows that education increases both agricultural diversification and diversification in INAS activities. Education levels likely reflect individual skills that are useful in multiple farm activities. Enhancing education is key to support diversification strategies. Lastly, it is worth mentioning that household couples who both work in the farm increased the likelihood of diversification. A first explanation might be larger self-consumption, as a couple running a farm is more likely to self-produce the goods they consume. In Italy, some evidence indicates that self-consumption is a growing trend not only in micro farms but also in medium-sized enterprises that adopt income diversification strategies. A second explanation is that when the owner's partner work in the same farm, the household has only one source of income, therefore diversification of the business is crucial to stabilize the family's cash flow. Third, running a farm as a couple increases the available workforce that be allocated to multiple tasks.

5 | Conclusions

Agriculture is affected by several structural risks, such as natural hazard, climate change, and volatile market prices, which

make the agricultural business especially risky. This problem is exacerbated in rural and remote areas, where agriculture is still relevant for local economies. Diversification is useful to stabilize agricultural income and might be implemented in different ways: crop diversification; on-farm diversification with activities connected with agricultural practices; off-farm diversification with an employment outside the farm business. This paper concentrated on crop and INAS activities options only, with the objective of understanding the impact of remoteness. For Italian farms, remoteness was defined with two broad measures, both equally important: a geographical indicator of remoteness (i.e., location in mountain areas), and a socioeconomic indicator (i.e., location in inner areas according to NSIA). The analysis showed that crop diversification is significantly larger in inner areas, but this difference is rather small. Conversely, with respect to INAS activities, farms in inner areas are not equally diversified, except farms in inner mountain areas. This result suggests that farms in inner areas may suffer from income fluctuation more than other types of farms. Thus, encouraging farms' diversification in INAS activities should be a policy goal, as they decouple the overall farm income from the uncertainty of farm productions. To this end, several policy measures might play a role, at both national and EU level.

In particular, over time, the CAP has largely contributed to promoting both forms of diversification for farms. In the 2014–2020 programming period, a payment for a compulsory set of greening measures was introduced, which accounts for 30 percent of the direct payments budget. Among others, the greening measures comprised crop diversification for larger farms (European Commission 2013). This prescription is also included in the current 2021–2027 programming period, as part of the enhanced conditionality. Similarly, since 2007, the Rural Development Policy of the CAP has supported investments in agricultural holdings for diversification into nonagricultural activities, for example, social, tourist, environmental, territorial, landscape, and food. In Italy, the support of agritourism and social agriculture activities is an important contributing factor to the incredible development observed in the years 2010s (Giaccio et al. 2018).

Despite the successes in fostering diversification of some EU policies, this study recommends further efforts in promoting agricultural diversification while ensuring food security, particularly in a shifting geopolitical and economic landscape. Additionally, agricultural diversification helps sustainability as it reduces farmers' dependence on high yields and increase income from nonconsumptive activities. Looking ahead to the post-2027 programming period, future reforms of the CAP should focus on fostering more sustainable agricultural practices, while also considering the existing regional differences across the EU. In this regard, the adaptability of agricultural EU policies to regional and specific contexts is necessary, to improve their overall effectiveness in meeting the EU's environmental goals. Hence, precise targeting and tailoring of rural and agricultural measures would be beneficial, especially for farms in inner and remote areas that are vulnerable to tough market conditions. Strengthening the integration between EU-level and national regional policies is also crucial. For example, a better alignment of nationwide policies (such as the NSIA) within existing rural policy frameworks is of utmost importance.

While this study generated interesting results, there are also some limitations to consider in their interpretation. A first limitation is that diversification in INAS activities is only proxied by the amount of working time allocated to them by the farmer. In general, all studies that investigate INAS activities approximate diversification with some indicators, and all indicators have positive aspects and drawbacks. In this case, working time dedicated to secondary activities is a proxy that does not fully reflect their economic importance within the total farm income. Subject to data availability, future research should consider the economic relevance of secondary activities to better inform policy on the difference in agricultural practices between inner and non-inner areas. Another limitation is the use of inner areas for relative remoteness, which is specific to the Italian case. However, NSIA includes a set of remoteness indicators that applies generally, and may be of interest to other stakeholders. Future research should also consider more refined indicators of remoteness, to obtain even more generalizable results.

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Ethics Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data for this analysis are the 7th agricultural census data of Italian farms. Census data cannot be downloaded or shared by authors. However, anyone can use census data upon request by contacting the Italian statistical office (ISTAT).

Endnotes

- ¹Berry Index and concentration ratio indices are also calculated and used for robustness checks. These models provide similar results and are not included in the manuscript. However, they are available upon request.
- ²Sub-categories of crops (e.g., durum wheat and soft wheat) are not considered. While census data contain this piece of information, the small size of most farm would made this computation very difficult. We believe that group categories are a good approximation of diversification as a risk-reduction tool because price correlation is lower than subcategory products.
- ³The count of activities is another metric used for diversification, which has been used by Pfeifer et al. (2009), Boncinelli et al. (2018), and Bartolini et al. (2014). Unfortunately, in this analysis, count models do not converge when using census data, presumably due to the excessive number of zeros in the dataset.
- ⁴The level of support payment is available in the dataset as an aggregated figure that includes the whole support from the Common

Agricultural Policy, namely including both the direct payments and the subsidies from Rural Development Policy.

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